

DEEP REGOLITH SOUNDER ON UEA'S LUNAR ROVER MISSION RASHID 3

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Mission Introduction: The Emirates Lunar Mission (ELM), led by the Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre (MBRSC), is a national initiative launched in 2019 to support global lunar exploration through lightweight, cost-effective rovers [1], [2]. Following Rashid 1 and the upcoming Rashid 2 [3], MBRSC is developing Rashid 3, its third rover, which will target the lunar south polar region — an area of high scientific interest due to indications of water ice in permanently shadowed regions (PSRs).

The Rashid 3 mission has two main scientific objectives: to investigate the geographical and geological characteristics of the moon's south polar region and to explore the presence of water on the surface and below it in the regolith layer and adjacent subsurface. To better understand the history of water in the Moon's evolution and to quantify the amount of water accessible in the shallow subsurface of the Moon, the Rashid 3 rover is equipped with seven lightweight scientific instruments.

The instrument Deep Regolith Sounder (DRS) is an ultra-wideband ground-penetrating radar (GPR) system developed for the integration into small planetary rovers and optimized for Rashid 3.

Deep Regolith Sounder: DRS consists of a compact radar electronics box and a lightweight, flat, linearly polarized antenna mounted beneath the rover. The instrument is designed and tested to achieve key scientific objectives, including the characterization of near-surface stratigraphy, detection of subsurface ice and cavities, and mapping of geological structures relevant to planetary evolution and in-situ resource utilization (ISRU). It's extremely compact electronics, occupying less than half a CubeSat unit (Fig. 1), operates across a frequency range of 10 MHz to 6 GHz, enabling high-resolution imaging over varying penetration depths.

Figure 1: Deep Regolith Sounder Electronics Box

The electronics system consists of two independent transmit and two independent receive channels (Fig. 2), allowing simultaneous full-polarimetric measurements to enhance material differentiation beneath the surface. The two transmission channels provide a 90-degree phase shift across the entire frequency range, enabling the transmission of circular polarization. The two independent reception channels directly measure the in-phase and quadrature (IQ) components of the received echo, allowing both the evaluation of amplitude and phase of the complex signal received by the DRS antenna.

Figure 2: Block diagram of the dual-channel IQ design of the Deep Regolith Sounder Electronics

The lightweight linear polarized DRS antenna (Fig. 3) on the Rashid 3 rover has a weight of less than 200 grams and is mounted below the rover. It covers a frequency range from 200 MHz to 6 GHz.

Figure 3: Deep Regolith Sounder Antenna

The antenna performance is affected by frequency-dependent coupling with the rover structure and variations in the dielectric properties of the regolith. This requires both an advanced signal processing and calibration algorithms to mitigate these effects and improve spatial resolution despite the small dimensions of the antenna and the rover.

Instrument Performance and Scientific Goals:

The radar is based on a Frequency-Modulated Continuous-Wave (FMCW) architecture and offers highly flexible operations, for example through variable

measurement speed settings. Moreover, it possesses an advanced gating function to improve the system's dynamic range, particularly for deep subsurface investigations. Depending on the antenna configuration, platform integration, and local geophysical properties, the radar can probe depths of tens of meters, while achieving a centimeter-scale resolution in near-surface layers. Due to its high sensitivity, it is particularly well suited for detecting ice-rich regolith and buried pockets of water ice, as the contrast between ice and regolith produces clearly visible radar reflections.

Special attention is currently being paid to the permanently shadowed regions (PSRs) at the South Pole of the Moon — areas that have not received sunlight for billions of years. These regions and the partially shadowed areas, which have complex light and temperature conditions, act as cold traps for volatiles and particularly water ice, which is crucial for future human exploration and resource utilization.

The DRS will map subsurface structures, determine the thickness of the regolith layer, and detect the presence of water ice at depths of several tens of meters. With bandwidths of > 5 GHz, the system achieves a resolution of better than 2 cm near the surface, while operation at lower frequencies allows penetration depths of several tens of meters, depending on local dielectric properties, with reduced resolution in the decimeter range. The radar offers a dynamic range of > 150 dB with an output power of up to 2 W and adjustable sweep times ranging from sub-milliseconds to seconds.

Performance Tests: Field tests in glacial and permafrost regions of Svalbard have shown that DRS can achieve a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio for subsurface imaging and estimating losses of lunar regolith. Further DRS-instrument tests were performed in the ESA/DLR Lunar Analogue Facility at DLR Cologne [4], where the different radar targets were buried and detected in Lunar regolith simulant.

Conclusions: The high-performance, extremely broadband DRS radar electronics was developed for integration into small platforms, and, despite their very small size and low weight, it offers great flexibility in terms of operation and provides a vast dynamic range. Together with the ultra-light antenna solution specially adapted to the Rashid 3 rover, DRS enables the provision of high-resolution data from the shallow and deep subsurface. DRS is particularly suitable for the use on small mobile platforms. It greatly supports scientific research for future small scientific and robot-assisted lunar rover missions such as Rashid 3.

References:

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